

USE OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN TEACHING THE NATIVE LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY GRADES

Nisanbayeva Akmaral

**Professor, National Pedagogical University
of Uzbekistan named after Nizami**

Utebaeva Altinshah

**Student, National Pedagogical University
of Uzbekistan named after Nizami**

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One of the most important principles of didactics is taking into account the age-related and individual characteristics of learners in the educational process. Primary school students already possess certain ideas about the objects and phenomena surrounding them and the relationships between these elements. They are capable of expressing their feelings and perceptions verbally. At this stage, their oral, written, and independent thinking skills begin to develop, and initial forms of abstract analysis and synthesis gradually emerge.

When organizing independent work, it is advisable to assign tasks that progress from simple to complex, taking into consideration the students' abilities and their readiness to work independently. Independent tasks can be conducted mainly in Grades 3 and 4.

In organizing independent work, the teacher may select a text and conduct a “Selective Dictation” exercise followed by several questions, such as:

Identify and analyze the adjectives and verbs in the text.

What distinguishes adjectives from verbs?

Which questions do adjectives answer?

Which questions do verbs answer?

What syntactic function do verbs perform in a sentence?

Such questions create a foundation for developing students' independent thinking skills.

When organizing independent work, the method of “small group work” can be effectively used by incorporating the game “Lucky Doors.” All students participate in this activity. The rules of the game are as follows:

Three doors are drawn on the board, and the class is divided into groups. Each door contains two questions related to parts of speech.

Questions for Door 1:

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the organization of independent work in native language lessons in primary grades. In particular, the purpose of teaching independent work on oneself is scientifically and practically justified by the fact that tasks are given from simple to complex.

Identify the words denoting actions: (Translated with the meaning of each word)

- **Artyapti** — *is cleaning / is wiping*
- **Rahmat** — *thank you* (not an action)
- **Yolg'iz** — *alone* (not an action)
- **Qochdi** — *ran away*
- **Yedi** — *ate*
- **Hasan** — *Hasan* (proper noun, not an action)
- **Bog'bon** — *gardener* (not an action)
- **Bordi** — *went*
- Identify the action characteristic of humans:
 - Kiyindi** — *got dressed*
 - Uxladi** — *slept*
 - Kishnadi** — *neighed* (action of a horse)
 - Cho'qidi** — *pecked* (action of a bird)
 - Sayradi** — *sang / chirped* (action of birds)
 - Suzdi** — *swam*

Groups that answer correctly proceed to Door 2.

Questions for Door 2:

Identify the words denoting qualities or characteristics of objects (adjectives):

- Qizil** — *red*
- To'rtburchak** — *rectangular*
- Soqol** — *beard* (not an adjective)
- Tanga** — *coin*
- Ko'ylak** — *shirt*
- Tugma** — *button*

Solve the riddle:

"Yozda kiyinadi, It dresses in summer,
Qishda yechinadi." Undresses in winter.

Possible answers:

- Suv** — *water*
- Daraxt** — *tree* ✓ (typical answer)
- Shamol** — *wind*
- Piyoz** — *onion*
- Gilam** — *carpet*

Questions for Door 3:

Identify positive (affirmative) verbs:

- Xushhabar** — *good news* (not a verb)
- Tinglamoq** — *to listen*
- Suzdi** — *swam*
- Yozdi** — *wrote*
- Bormadi** — *did not go* (negative)
- Uxladi** — *slept*

Identify negative verbs:

- **Yozmadi** *did not write*
- **Bajarmadi** *did not perform / did not complete*
- **Foydalandi** *used (affirmative)*
- **Yig`ladi** *cried (affirmative)*

At the end of the game, the winning group is rewarded. This activity is particularly useful when studying the parts of speech “adjective” and “verb.”

The use of such interactive games in organizing independent tasks helps students express their thoughts freely and independently, develops their speech, enriches their vocabulary, expands their thinking, teaches them to listen to one another, and strengthens their understanding of the material covered.

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